

Rituals in Nuclear Statecraft: Conjuring Conformity, Cohesion, and Cooperation

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Nuclear statecraft is often seen as a field of policy characterized by hyper-rationality and icy reserve. Yet the practices that make it up are shot through with symbolic imagery and ritualistic behavior. Seeking to advance the nascent literature on ritual in world politics, this article offers an investigation into the origins and functions of central rites in nuclear policy practice. Arguing that rituals can help conjure conformity, cohesion, and cooperation in contexts where credibility is scarce and preferences are at loggerheads, I explore how rituals are deployed to overcome key problems in nuclear statecraft, including the challenge of maintaining obedience throughout the nuclear chain of command, the imperative of securing international buy-in for controversial policies, and the difficulties associated with facilitating structured communication between adversarial states. To do so, I examine three empirical cases: Russian nuclear deterrence practice, NATO's Nuclear Planning Group, and multilateral nuclear disarmament diplomacy at the UN.

L'habileté politique nucléaire est souvent perçue comme un domaine politique caractérisé par une rationalité démesurée et une réserve glaciale. Pourtant, les pratiques qui la constituent sont empreintes d'une imagerie symbolique et de comportements rituels. Afin de faire progresser la littérature émergente sur le rituel en politique mondiale, cet article propose une enquête sur les origines et fonctions des rites centraux dans la pratique politique nucléaire. Affirmant que les rituels peuvent permettre de faire apparaître de la conformité, de la cohésion et de la coopération dans des contextes où la crédibilité se fait rare et les préférences divergent, je m'intéresse au déploiement des rituels afin de surmonter des problèmes clés en politique nucléaire, notamment le défi du maintien de l'obéissance tout au long de la chaîne de commandement nucléaire, l'impératif de l'obtention de l'adhésion internationale aux politiques polémiques et les difficultés associées à la facilitation d'une communication structurée entre États opposés. Pour ce faire, j'examine trois cas empiriques : les pratiques de dissuasion nucléaire de la Russie, le Groupe des plans nucléaires de l'OTAN et la diplomatie multilatérale de désarmement nucléaire à l'ONU.

Con frecuencia, se percibe al arte de la política nuclear como un campo de políticas caracterizado por la hiperracionalidad y por una fría cautela. Sin embargo, las prácticas que lo componen están impregnadas de imágenes simbólicas y de comportamientos rituales. Este artículo busca proporcionar avances a la naciente literatura relativa a los rituales en la política mundial. Para ello, este artículo ofrece una investigación sobre los orígenes y las funciones de los ritos fundamentales en la práctica de la política nuclear. Argumentamos que los rituales pueden ayudar a conjurar conformidad, cohesión y cooperación en contextos donde la credibilidad es escasa y las preferencias se encuentran en desacuerdo. Esto nos permite analizar cómo se utilizan los rituales para superar problemas clave en el ámbito de la política nuclear, incluyendo el desafío de mantener la obediencia a lo largo de la cadena de mando nuclear, la necesidad de asegurar el apoyo internacional para políticas controvertidas y las dificultades asociadas con facilitar una comunicación estructurada entre Estados adversarios. Con el fin de llevar esto a cabo, analizamos tres casos empíricos: las prácticas en materia de disuasión nuclear rusa, el Grupo de Planificación Nuclear de la OTAN y la diplomacia de desarme nuclear multilateral en la ONU.

Keywords: Ritual; enchantment; nuclear deterrence; disarmament; ideology.

Introduction

Nuclear statecraft is often seen as a field of policy characterized by its practitioners' cool reserve and stripped-down economic rationality. According to one observer, the strategic paradigm that underpins the nuclear policies of the major powers reflects a system of "instrumental, utilitarian reason" (Burke 2009, 512). According to another, the "nuclear system" is defined by a form of "hyper-rationality" enacted with a view to merging security and defense with planetary-scale violence (Masco 2015, 30). In her celebrated article on Cold War defense intellectuals, Carol Cohn (1987, 702) describes the nuclear-strategic epistemic community as a subculture "that claims as a sign of its superiority its vigilant purging of all nonrational elements, and in which people carefully excise from their discourse every possible trace of soft sentimentality." Yet, as both Cohn and others have observed, nu-

clear discourse is heavily inflected by the numinous (Cohn 1987; Taylor 2022, 158). Many of the most central expressions of nuclear politics take the form of stylized, symbolic performances that might productively be read as rites or ceremonies. Ritual is everywhere in nuclear statecraft.

Seeking to advance the nascent literature on ritual and ritualization in world politics, this article investigates the origins and functions of central rites in nuclear policy practice. Arguing that rituals can help generate conformity, cohesion, and cooperation in contexts where credibility is scarce and preferences are often at loggerheads, I explore how rituals are deployed to overcome key problems in nuclear statecraft, including the challenge of fostering obedience throughout the nuclear chain of command, the imperative of securing allied buy-in for controversial policies, and the difficulties associated with facilitating structured communication between adversarial states. The cases serve as "illustrative

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cases” or “plausibility probes” and are selected to showcase the value of applying ritual-theoretic perspectives on varied nuclear policy practices (see [Levy 2008](#), 6). The cases are not meant to systematically “test” a theory but, more modestly, to tease out the potential benefits of viewing nuclear statecraft through the lens of ritual theory. As established in social science methodology literature, plausibility probes provide useful first steps when exploring the payoff of applying a particular theory to a given subject area ([Eckstein 2000](#), 141–2). Using ritual theory to examine nuclear statecraft, I suggest, calls attention to underexplored nuclear practices and helps shed light on longstanding debates in security studies. Crucially, my findings are of significant relevance for the debate between deterrence optimists and pessimists, that is, the disagreement between those who see nuclear deterrence as relatively easy to achieve and those who view it as “delicate” and fraught with difficulty (see [Deudney 2018](#)). While members of the latter group have typically highlighted material vulnerabilities and the attendant difficulties associated with maintaining a robust retaliatory capability (see, e.g., [Wohlstetter 1959](#); [Green 2020](#); [Lieber and Press 2020](#)), a ritual-theoretic reading of deterrence spotlights the *social* difficulties at the heart of nuclear statecraft.

The pervasiveness of ritual in nuclear statecraft corroborates a view of nuclear policy that sees nuclear deterrence as loaded with political tensions and credibility problems. Aiming to complement and advance the existing literature on how norms, discourses, and culture shape nuclear politics (see, e.g., [Engström 2014](#); [Ritchie 2019](#); [Considine 2022](#)), I connect ritual theory to theories of ideology and ideological reproduction in the nuclear domain ([Egeland 2021](#); [Ritchie 2024](#)). A key function of ritual, I maintain, is to sustain particular worldviews and power structures, i.e., to (re)produce certain ways of doing, seeing, and justifying political actions ([Sloterdijk 1987](#); [Althusser 2014](#)). Deciphering the way power is constituted in the world of nuclear statecraft is of great urgency and importance in a time marked by intensifying military competition and nuclearized conflicts involving major powers. My central claim is that the discourses and ideology that sustain the extant nuclear order are reified through the performance by nuclear policy practitioners of routinized, symbol-heavy performances.

The article proceeds in three steps. In the first part, I lay out ritual theory and the concepts informing the investigation to follow. In the second part, drawing on archival documents, secondary literature, and insider accounts, I examine three empirical cases: the deployment by the Russian nuclear security state of explicit religious rituals, the origins and workings of NATO’s formal nuclear consultation arrangement, and the practice of multilateral nuclear disarmament diplomacy at the UN. The various sources used are drawn upon pragmatically to examine the role of ritual in nuclear statecraft. In the third and final part, I summarize the findings and reflect on the relevance of ritual theory to students of global nuclear politics and strategy.

The Form and Functions of Ritual

Rituals are notoriously difficult to define but have been usefully conceptualized as “formalized social set-piece performances” (ref: introduction to the special issue) or “repetitious and stylized” actions typically centered on “cosmic structures and/or sacred presences” ([Zuesse 1987](#), 405). According to [Jonathan Smith \(1987](#), 109), “ritual is, above all, an assertion of difference,” meaning that rituals provide a framework for distinguishing between the ordinary, on the one hand, and the extraordinary or particularly meaningful, on

the other. Rituals help infuse or “enchant” otherwise mundane doings and sayings with metaphysical content. The Eucharist, for example, is a religious ritual that frames the consumption of bread and wine as spiritual, rather than mere physical, nourishment ([Bell 1990](#), 303). Rituals can be religious, cultural, social, or personal in nature. They have been found to be ubiquitous in human societies, including in diplomatic settings, where rituals have been argued to promote cooperation and ordered interaction between distinct and often antagonistic polities ([Holmes and Wheeler 2020](#); [Balzacq 2020](#)). Ritual practices typically display features such as formalism, traditionalism, disciplined routines, rule-governance, sacral symbolism, and embodied performance ([Bell 1997](#); [Mälksoo 2021](#), 55). Rituals can emerge either through a process whereby extant practices are associated with sacredly held values (ref: introduction to this special issue) or through the deliberate putting into action of prescribed set-piece events ([Bell 1990](#)).

The notion that rituals are typically centered on “cosmic structures and/or sacred presences” has often been pushed to the background in applications of ritual theory to international relations and diplomacy ([Balzacq 2020](#), 114). But, in the nuclear sphere, the numinous is never far away. Indeed, nuclear policy discourse is peppered with references to the “cosmic” implications of nuclear technology (see, e.g., [Ball 1983](#)), allusions to divine “mystery” ([Kinsella 2005](#), 51), and metaphors invoking “the Bomb as God” ([Hymans 2024](#)). The world’s first-ever nuclear explosive test, “Trinity,” was named after John Donne’s devotional poem “Holy Sonnets” ([Templeton 2021](#)). Witnessing the test, J. Robert Oppenheimer, the man in charge, claims to have recalled a line from the Hindu scripture: “Now I am become Death, the destroyer of worlds” ([Atomic Heritage 2015](#)). The first major contribution to the established canon of nuclear strategic thinking framed the bomb as the “absolute” weapon ([Brodie 1946](#)). All-out nuclear war has frequently been framed in eschatological terms, with the Christian vision of Armageddon, the Islamic notion of Al-Malhama Al-Kubra, and the Norse idea of Ragnarök providing conceptual vehicles of sense-making ([Ausmus 1998](#), 71). Below, I argue that rituals and ritualization in nuclear statecraft have helped “enchant” nuclear weapons as sublime instruments of security (ref: introduction to the special issue).

Rituals reify and allow relevant stakeholders to act out symbols and assumptions about social and metaphysical relations. Thus conceived, rituals do not “symbolize x, but actualize it” (ref: introduction to the special issue). Taking this one step further, and drawing on Peter Sloterdijk’s theory of ideology, rituals can be interpreted as bearers of ideological content, structuring individuals’ interface with the world. According to [Sloterdijk \(1987](#), 5–6), many ideologies, particularly in the modern world, are sustained not because individuals actively believe in their precepts or underlying assumptions (contra: the introduction to the special issue), but because of a sense of “cynical reason”—a belief that resistance would be socially uncomfortable, dangerous, or futile. Even fully “enlightened” subjects, Sloterdijk suggests, will most likely resign themselves to acquiescing to the dominant social practices and thus to upholding the prevailing ideology. In this view, the maintenance of an ideology or political paradigm does not depend on what actors privately believe, but on what they do in practice. Rituals, in short, are expressions and carriers of ideology (cf. [Eagleton 1991](#); [Althusser 2014](#); [Kustermans 2019](#)). That said, the explicit intent behind specific rituals is often fuzzy, and there is a large body of literature exploring the emancipatory potential of rituals (see, e.g., [Bell 1990](#), 311; [Eddins 2022](#)). Either way, rituals provide

ways of performing and exercising power (ref: introduction to the special issue).

Rituals can serve various spoken and unspoken social functions. I maintain that, on an overall level, rituals have helped produce nuclear weapons and deterrence practices as “sublime,” that is, as awe-inspiring, numinous objects or doings beyond the direct comprehension of humans—or at any rate the general public (Dahl 1985; Masco 2004, 3). More generally, Catherine Bell (1990, 299) maintains that ritual has “a type of efficacy of power—not the power that it might claim, but a special ability to shape social organization and thereby the disposition of individuals.” A first social function of ritual is that of fostering social bonding or cohesion. Rituals can help create a sense of shared identity and belonging among participants. Whether in religious ceremonies, civic events, or cultural celebrations, collective engagement in ritual activities often generates a feeling of unity. Émile Durkheim’s concept of “collective effervescence” aptly captures the heightened emotional intensity experienced during rituals. Collective effervescence, Durkheim (1995) suggests, works to strengthen the social ties that bind individuals together and, by implication, promote social conformity and group agency. Participating in rituals frequently fosters a sense of “us” versus “them,” delineating the boundaries that define a community (see, e.g., Wombacher and Felfe 2012). By contrast, ritual failure can induce social rupture (Koschut 2024).

A second function often attributed to rituals, a function that overlaps with but is not reducible to the first, is that of transmitting or perpetuating cultural values, traditions, and ideologies across time and space. Through symbolic actions and narratives, rituals can project the supposed essence of a community’s beliefs and norms. Rites of passage, religious ceremonies, and cultural celebrations often become mnemonic conduits for cultural continuity, ensuring that the received—and often supernaturally sanctioned—“heritage” and “collective wisdom” of a society are passed down and preserved over the generations (Bell 1990, 308). In this sense, rituals embody what Michael Barnett and Raymond Duvall (2005, 55) term “productive power,” that is, the power to constitute subjects and their self-understandings. In the literature on ritual, productive or constitutive rituals are often described as “liminal” (Koschut 2024).

A third function of ritual is that of regulating social interactions and order. From legal ceremonies and civic rituals to the traditions embedded in organizational and bureaucratic settings, rituals can serve to establish a sense of order and predictability. They create a shared understanding of societal norms and expectations, reinforcing the rules that govern social interactions and relationships. As suggested above, rituals have been central to diplomacy for centuries or even millennia. In fact, some of the very first accounts of diplomatic interactions describe ritualistic behavior, such as symbolic gift-giving and the paying of homage to rival polities’ gods (Neumann and Glørstad 2022). To this day, diplomatic behaviors frequently display ritualistic features, with rules of precedence, incantations of formulaic phrases, and symbolic handshakes giving structure to formal meetings and proceedings.¹

A fourth and final function of ritual, which has been persuasively demonstrated in experimental psychology, is that of providing a framework for coping with stress and adversity. For example, Michael Norton and Francesca Gino found in a 2014 experiment that mourners who engaged in griev-

ing rituals reported lower levels of grief than those who did not. “Increased feelings of control after rituals mediated the link between use of rituals and reduced grief after losses, and the benefits of rituals accrued not only to individuals who professed a belief in rituals’ effectiveness but also those who did not” (Norton and Gino 2014, 266). Along similar lines, engagement in rituals has been found to boost employees’ perception of the meaningfulness of their work (Kim et al. 2021) and to enhance behavioral self-control and a sense of agency in the face of difficult circumstances (Tian et al. 2018).

Ritualizing Atomic Practices, Enchanting Nuclear Statecraft

Nuclear statecraft is shot through with ritual. But what, exactly, are the functions of these rituals? And how did they emerge? This section dives into three areas of nuclear statecraft to illustrate the value of adopting a ritual-theoretic lens on nuclear politics.

Russian Nuclear Orthodoxy

The first case analyzed in this study is the Russian military’s active incorporation of explicit religious rituals and imagery in its nuclear deterrence practices. Following the collapse of communism, Russian citizens and leaders began searching for new sources of meaning to help validate and find purpose in political practices and institutions. These would eventually be found in the form of carefully curated reconstructions of Russian military history and the country’s Christian Orthodox heritage (Anderson 2007; Neumann 2016; McGlynn 2023). The Soviet Union had effectively dropped its anti-religious commitment by 1990, leading to a revitalization of existing religious elements as well as an influx of new religious groups and sects toward the end of the communist period. The flourishing of smaller sects ultimately provoked a strong counterreaction, however, with nationalist politicians and leaders of the predominant Orthodox Church expressing concerns about religious-cultural fragmentation. In 1997, the Russian Duma adopted a new law that imposed restrictions on minority religions and empowered the Orthodox Church. The period saw a pronounced religious revival among the Russian population at large as well as a budding realignment of Church and state (Evans and Northmore-Ball 2012).

Having been inaugurated as president of the Russian Federation during the early afternoon of May 7, 2000, the new president’s very first order of business was to attend a religious service at the Cathedral of the Annunciation a short walk from the Grand Kremlin Palace. At the service, Patriarch Alexy II, the primate of Russian Orthodoxy, praised Russia’s new leader and invited him to “help us to disclose the soul of the nation” (Anderson 2007, 185). In January of that year, Putin, then acting president, had maintained in his Christmas greeting to Orthodox believers that the ideals of the Russian Orthodox Church would help strengthen a national consensus and “contribute to the spiritual and moral rebirth of the Fatherland” (Anderson 2007, 188). Over the course of the succeeding years, the Orthodox Church would gain in political prominence and visibility. That said, the alignment of Church and state would remain largely unofficial, distinct from Peter the Great’s direct subordination of the Church to the Russian state apparatus 300 years before.

The Russian Orthodox Church’s increasing salience in Russian political life after the collapse of the Soviet Union influenced not only domestic politics and discussions of moral

¹Handshaking has been found in experimental psychology to promote deal-making. See Schroeder et al. (2019).

values but also Russian military and foreign policy practices. The unofficial integration of the Orthodox Church into the Russian Armed Forces had begun in 1994, when the Church came to an agreement with the Russian Ministry of Defense concerning the provision by the former of military chaplains to Russian military units (Knox 2005, 123). The underlying motivation was the supposed importance of the Orthodox faith for “the morale and efficacy” of Russian service members. In the words of Archbishop Kirill, who would go on to succeed Alexy II as primate of the Russian Orthodox Church in 2009, “one of the tasks of the church in its special ministry is to teach and confirm in people spiritual and moral principles which will make them worthy people and stalwart defenders of the Fatherland” (Knox 2005, 124).

In 2000, Archbishop Kirill and then Russian Deputy Minister of Defense N. V. Mikhailov together launched a Department of Orthodox Culture at the Russian Military Academy at Smolensk. Kirill had been appointed an honorary professor at the Smolensk Academy four years before (Information Service of the Serbian Orthodox Church 2014), and from 2000 onward the department would offer courses in Orthodox culture and religion to military officers in training (Knox 2005, 124). The establishment of the Department of Orthodox Culture at Smolensk constituted an important milestone in a process that saw the Russian Orthodox Church given an increasingly prominent, state-sanctioned role as a provider of “spiritual and moral education” for military and law-enforcement workers (Knox 2005, 124). Over time, similar theological departments would pop up in other military academies across Russia, including the Military Academy of the Strategic Rocket Forces located in Balashikha in Moscow Oblast (Gorenburg 2012). In fact, the Russian military-nuclear complex has gone further than other sections of the Russian military in incorporating religious elements in its quotidian practices and ceremonies. This development has been actively supported by influencers championing a doctrine of “Atomic Orthodoxy,” a belief that Russian Orthodox civilization requires protection from foreign aggression, degeneracy, and decadence by a strong, nuclear-armed state (Engström 2014). According to Maria Engström (2014, 359), Russian neoconservative intellectuals believe strongly in “conjunction,” that is, the “creative, ritualistic” force of words and images. Art, literature, and rites of various forms are meant to enchant and summon—to actively produce desirable cultural-political outcomes, such as the defense of the fatherland by devout, nuclear-armed Russians.

As detailed by Dima Adamsky (2019), each leg of the Russian nuclear triad (land-based nuclear forces, sea-based nuclear forces, and the nuclear air force) has been assigned an official patron saint. (The concept of the “military three” has itself been theorized as an influence from the “magical threes of traditional myth and ritual” Mälksoo 2015, 331). The nuclear industry as such also has its saint, Seraphim of Sarov, “one of the most renowned Russian saints” (Adamsky 2019, 29). As a rule, religious icons decorate the insides of Russian nuclear submarines, bombers, and command posts. Formalized religious performances heavy with sacral symbolism, including ground processions of the cross, “are routine” at nuclear sites, and each big nuclear base sports a garrison church, chapel, or prayer room; mobile intercontinental ballistic missiles are accompanied by mobile temples. Religious holidays are diligently observed, and catechization is an integral part of military nuclear education. Orthodox priests are integrated in professional activities “through the whole chain of command,” taking part in operational missions on the ground and underwater (Adamsky 2019, 29). What is

more, representatives of the Church are regularly invited to sanctify Russian nuclear weapons and deterrence practices through explicit religious rituals (Adamsky 2019, 1).² Inter alia, this has involved recurring religious ceremonies whereby priests sprinkle holy water on nuclear submarines and missiles. While this practice has attracted some criticism from within the Orthodox clergy, its abandonment has been fiercely resisted. In 2022, a Russian archpriest insisted that a proposal to rein in the newfangled tradition of blessing nuclear weapons would “in no way” succeed (The Moscow Times 2023). The bodily performance by priests of religious rituals at military bases helps the nuclear complex connect military and religious discourses, reifying “atomic orthodoxy” through tangible material performances.

The invocation of religious and even eschatological imagery goes to the very top of the Russian nuclear state. For example, in his speech to the Valdai Discussion Club in 2018, President Putin exclaimed that anyone contemplating nuclear aggression against Russia “must know that retribution is inevitable, that he will be annihilated,” and that there would be “a global catastrophe.” However, “[a]s martyrs, we will go to heaven and they will just croak, because they won’t even have time to repent” (Gessen 2018). In 2022, former Russian President and current Deputy Chairman of the Russian Security Council, Dmitry Medvedev, described the Russian war against Ukraine and its Western backers as a sacred conflict with “the supreme ruler of Hell, whatever name he uses—Satan, Lucifer or Iblis.” Overtly hinting toward Russia’s nuclear arsenal, Medvedev added that Russia had the capability to “send all our enemies to fiery Gehenna” (Reuters 2022). In 2023, upon bestowing the Order of Saint Sergius of Radonezh upon Radiy Ilkaev, the head of Russia’s nuclear weapons production facility, Patriarch Kirill stated that, were it not for nuclear weapons, “it is difficult to say if our country would still exist.” Luckily, the “ineffable providence of God” had allowed Soviet scientists to develop nuclear weapons “under the protection of St. Seraphim of Sarov” (The Moscow Times 2023).

The integration of concrete, material religious rituals into Russian nuclear deterrence practice—the sprinkling of holy water on missiles, the installation of icons in bombers and submarines, etc.—could be argued to serve in at least three of the four functions discussed above. First, the performance and observance of material religious rituals at nuclear bases serve to ground and reify the high-flying religious propaganda statements of presidents and patriarchs, fostering social bonding—“collective effervescence”—at the level of soldiers, commanders, scientists, and other personnel. Collective effervescence could help build shared resolve and desire to protect the nation—even with extreme means. Military leaders’ denunciation of rivals and adversaries, particularly in wartime or during periods of heightened tension, has also been argued to constitute a ritual of “othering” that helps foster we-feeling and conformity among service members (Benford and Kurtz 1987, 471–2). Second, the performance of rituals could help individual soldiers cope with the more mundane, physical stresses of handling and being around weapons of mass destruction. Third, and perhaps most importantly, religious ritualization in the field of nuclear statecraft has allowed the Russian military-nuclear complex to enchant nuclear weapons as “sublime” or awe-inspiring instruments of cosmic, existential security (see Schwab 2020, 120).

²Of course, these rituals complement an existing and more basic array of military rituals (saluting, marching, combat training) and norms of “uniformity and conformity” (standardised dress, hierarchical rules). See Simpson (2002, 211).

Religious ritualization has helped entrench the idea that, in certain circumstances, the use of nuclear weapons would be not only morally and spiritually acceptable but also mandated. Indeed, [Adamsky \(2019, 241\)](#) theorizes that the exploitation of religious rituals and imagery in the service of the Russian nuclear state functions as a means of ensuring that personnel in the Russian nuclear chain of command will exorcise any moral or legal qualms associated with the use of nuclear weapons and execute launch orders if or when they are called upon to do so. The religious licensing of the use of nuclear weapons, in this view, functions to combat the problem of potential disobedience. This is a significant challenge in the context of nuclear weapons. After all, as one commentator puts it, the airman or weapons officer called upon to execute a nuclear launch order “may end up between the Charybdis of being shot for insubordination in war-time and the Scylla of being hanged, if a military tribunal organized by the victor decides that his act shocked the conscience of civilized peoples” ([Lewy 1961, 5](#)).

As [Nina Tannenwald \(2008\)](#), [T. V. Paul \(2009\)](#), [Thomas Schelling \(2006\)](#), and other scholars have shown, the threats and explicit talk of nuclear use have been increasingly (though not wholly) stigmatized over time. Religious rituals deployed to harden the resolve of soldiers and policymakers to use nuclear weapons in certain circumstances can thus be seen as a vehicle of counteracting this tendency and, by extension, enhancing the credibility of nuclear threats. The fact that religious rituals are present also in other areas of Russian military activity helps integrate the various activities enacted in service of Russia’s security into a larger, spiritually infused whole. In summary, nuclear orthodoxy appears to help buttress conformity throughout the Russian nuclear chain of command.

NATO’s Nuclear Planning Group

Nuclear policy was fraught within the Atlantic alliance from the very beginning. The disagreements concerned a myriad of issues, including targeting policy, launch authority, arms control and disarmament, the credibility of alternative military postures, and the basic role of nuclear weapons in Western defense ([Trachtenberg 1991](#); [Egeland 2020](#)). Certain allies, perhaps most notably Italy and West Germany, grew eager over the course of the 1950s and 1960s to increase their involvement in nuclear statecraft. Certain factions within these countries were also eager to explore the possibility of their respective states acquiring independent nuclear arsenals. Other members, perhaps most notably Denmark and Norway, were much more skeptical of the utility of nuclear weapons and certainly of intra-alliance proliferation.

An initial proposal for how these competing preferences might be reconciled was the idea of creating a multilateral nuclear force under joint NATO command. However, it was never clear precisely how this would work out in practice, and some members were staunchly opposed to turning NATO as such into a nuclear power. The eventual solution was the establishment of formal arrangements for dedicated consultations on nuclear policy. In December 1966, two new forums were created. These were the Nuclear Defence Affairs Committee (NDAC), a forum open to the ministers of defense of all NATO members, and the Nuclear Planning Group (NPG), a subsidiary and more hands-on organ of the NDAC made up of only seven member states (the United States, the United Kingdom, Italy, West Germany, and three additional interested states on a rotational basis). The two groups would eventually merge into a single, defense-ministerial organ open to all member states under the name of the Nuclear

Planning Group ([Gregory 1996, 31](#)). The NPG remains the only issue-specific ministerial-level committee within the alliance.

The official purpose of the nuclear consultation arrangement established in the mid-1960s was to allow for increased allied involvement in nuclear policymaking. Another driver behind the creation of the NDAC/NPG was the US government’s long-standing ambition to fully embed nuclear weapons in Western strategic culture ([Sayle 2019, 118](#)). Over the course of the 1950s, as fears rose about possible Soviet campaigns to “stigmatize and inhibit possible US use of its nuclear weapons capabilities even for self-defense” ([Davis 1954](#); [Joint Chiefs of Staff 1961](#)), influential US policymakers grew convinced that America needed to elicit greater and more visible allied support for its nuclear policies. This might be done, according to the Planning Board of the US National Security Council, through the adoption by the US government of a “policy of candor” that would give allies “a sense of shared responsibility through an increase in their understanding of the political and military implications of atomic weapons” ([National Security Council Planning Board 1953](#)).

According to one set of scholars, the NPG/NDAC was created “because then U.S. Secretary of Defense Robert McNamara sought to influence the thinking of allies on nuclear strategy and the new strategy of Flexible Response.” A key factor, they suggest, “was the United States’ desire to (re)build broader alliance cohesion” ([Frühling and O’Neil 2017, 12](#)). Looking back, it must be concluded that this desire has largely been satisfied. Despite conflicting government preferences and staunch anti-nuclear public sentiment in several member states, NATO has, with a few notable exceptions, maintained cohesion in most nuclear matters. But how? Several factors are likely to have played a role. For one thing, it has been clear to everyone involved that the senior partner in the alliance, the state most members look to as their security guarantor, places a high premium on its nuclear arsenal and does not take particularly kindly to criticism ([Egeland 2020](#)). For another, NATO’s basic rules of procedure demand that major decisions be made by consensus. This means that, once a policy has been put in place, it is enormously difficult for individual members to disown or dislodge it.

Beyond these more straightforward explanations, however, I suggest that ritual has played an important part in the conjuring of NATO cohesion on nuclear issues; or, in other words, that the annual (formerly semi-annual) meetings of the NPG can be read as a ritual. While the NPG has undoubtedly also played an “instrumental” role as a forum for information exchange, bargaining, and genuine debate ([Frühling and O’Neil 2017, 12](#))—at least early on—the Group has in more recent decades been described as a carefully choreographed “rubber-stamping body” that does not actually cater for meaningful political or strategic discussions ([Buteux 1983, 143](#)). According to one critic, “the formalities of “consultation” are tolerated [by US officials] as a relatively painless way of expediting American policy” ([Ramsbotham 1989, 146](#)). In the words of a more diplomatically inclined commentator on nuclear policy, “Washington certainly recognizes that there is much to be gained by observing the niceties of political discourse within a pluralistic political body such as NATO” ([Larsen 1991, 215](#)). Admittedly, upon establishing the NPG in 1966, McNamara encouraged his defense-minister colleagues to “discuss matters freely rather than rely on “some canned words” their staffs had prepared” ([Sayle 2019, 116](#)). As discussed above, however, the NPG was eventually subsumed into the NDAC (though under the NPG name), a forum that, in [Martin Smith’s \(2000, 29\)](#) words, had been “always intended to be a largely symbolic forum.” Ac-

cording to James Thomson (1994, 248), already by the second half of the 1970s, the NPG “had become more a ritual than an exchange of views on substantial issues.”

In a ritual-theoretic perspective, NATO’s nuclear consultation arrangement can be seen as a thick social institution displaying some of the key features of ritual, notably formalization, embodied performances, and sacral symbolism (see Mälksoo 2021, 55). The NPG provides a recurring formal encounter at which NATO defense ministers are obliged to physically turn up and look each other—and, crucially, the patriarchal figure of the US Secretary of Defense—in the eyes as they consult on the proper uses of the alliance’s “cosmic” weapon systems. There is a strong expectation that any resultant communiqués will reflect the member states’ unified view. The practice of “footnoting,” that is, when a member state expresses disagreement with a certain passage or paragraph within an alliance document (typically by flagging their disagreement through a footnote), is rare and strongly discouraged by institutional norms (Pedallu 2016). As a result, the Group largely functions to pass down received wisdom across new generations of defense policymakers. In this view, the NPG produces bonding (of the individuals involved) and ideological sustainment (of NATO’s nuclear deterrence strategy). The ideological sustainment functions largely through the liminal production of new practitioners (or supposed beneficiaries) of extended nuclear deterrence.

While the NPG is chaired by the NATO Secretary General, its meetings are, for obvious reasons, dominated by the United States. The US Secretary of Defense oversees more than 90 percent of the member states’ combined nuclear forces (though admittedly the White House exercises supreme control over launch decisions) and functions, for the purposes of the NPG, as the head of the US nuclear policy establishment, a community often referred to, including by some of its most prominent members (see, e.g., Payne 2023), as the “nuclear priesthood” (Arkin 1994; Hymans 2024). As in the Russian case, the US nuclear arsenal is grouped into a “holy trinity” (another magical three) of land-, sea-, and air-based nuclear weapons (Futter and Williams 2016). According to Lee Butler (1998, 58), who served as commander-in-chief of the US combatant command responsible for exercising nuclear deterrence (US Strategic Command), faith in nuclear weapons as useful and legitimate instruments of statecraft has been maintained, above all, by “a catechism instilled over many decades by a priesthood who spoke with assurance and authority” (see also, e.g., Egeland 2021; Ritchie 2024). US allies, Butler (1998, 60) claims, eventually “yielded to its dictates, even while decrying its risks and costs.” The NPG provided the central alliance forum for this process of reproductive cohesion-building and nuclear “education” (Sayle 2020). In this view, the NPG

institutionalized and legitimized major decisions [...]. This impacted on two important audiences for NATO: the Soviet Union, which could be expected to prefer a divided and rancorous Alliance to which it could direct divisive policy initiatives; and the European members’ publics, who would be more apt to accept the arguments given for a particular position if the Alliance seemed firmly behind it (Seay 2013, 2).

The NPG is frequently portrayed as an active and crucial policy-making organ. In reality, during the post-Cold War period, the NPG has typically convened only once a year for a relatively short session. The whole thing is over within one or two hours. The encounter begins with the ritual exchange of smiles and handshakes to build intimacy and effervescence. Then the participants withdraw to a secluded space, isolated from the outside world and any potential counter-rituals by protestors, and the meeting can get underway. The

main event is usually a briefing from the US Secretary of Defense. In contrast to other NATO events, where the taking of a post-meeting “family portrait” has become an important ritual (Koschut 2024, 294), the NPG maintains a low media profile, possibly contributing to the sense of mystique that characterizes the nuclear realm. According to Jacques Hymans (2024, 8–9), nuclear politics is plagued by a “divine mystery” metaphor that makes nuclear weapons seem “simultaneously all-important and beyond our ken.” The mystery metaphor complicates efforts to treat nuclear arms as mundane things that can be used or discarded as we please, Hymans argues, framing them instead as objects to be looked upon with “fear, awe, and sometimes also “the satisfaction found in absolute surrender to the larger power.”” Not unlike the religious rituals discussed above, the NPT has helped enchant nuclear weapons as sublime or numinous instruments of extended deterrence.

The NPG is not the only NATO or international forum to display ritual features, of course. NATO summits have often been described as arenas for symbolic performances and the projection of “precooked” talking points and “ritualistic platitudes” (Smith 2000; Simpson 2002, 78, 117). Practices that from a rational military perspective might appear redundant or mundane are frequently identified as symbolically significant. For example, several observers have argued that the US nuclear gravity bombs stationed in Europe have little or no military value, serving primarily as “symbols of the transatlantic relationship” (Suchy and Thayer 2014, 509). In summary, the NPG has served to enhance the NATO members’ cohesion on nuclear issues.

Multilateral Nuclear Arms Control Diplomacy

Diplomatic practice at the various international forums that make up multilateral nuclear arms control and disarmament diplomacy—notably the UN General Assembly’s First Committee, the Conference on Disarmament, the Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT) review process, the Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW) meetings of states party, and the Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban-Treaty Organization’s Preparatory Commission (CTBTO)—also displays some of the central features of ritual. Not only are the meetings in question endlessly recurring—some have been running for three-quarters of a century—but also the proceedings at these arenas are heavily formalized and rule-governed, the discourses that circulate display sacral symbolism, and the diplomats involved act out prescribed bodily performances, most notably the reading out of formal statements on behalf of states, multinational blocs of states, or international organizations. These statements often resemble ritualistic incantations, with certain words and phrases, such as references to the NPT as the “cornerstone” of the nuclear nonproliferation and disarmament regime, being repeated over and over again (Considine 2020; see also Oren and Solomon 2015). Individual conferences usually follow the same basic script, with the election of the chairperson or president followed by opening statements, committee work, and then positioning vis-à-vis a final document, communiqué, or series of resolutions. Analyzing the NPT review cycle, Ursula Jasper (2016, 45) concludes that the institutional processes of the nonproliferation regime “resembles a “religious field”—i.e., a deeply anchored, static structure that relies on ritualistic practices for its preservation.” Christopher Daese (2003, 27), similarly, describes the NPT review process as a platform for the ritual performance of the regime’s norms.

Multilateral nuclear arms control and disarmament conferences are invariably somewhat dull. Most states' general statements draw heavily on past interventions and are commonly produced on the basis of input from various ministerial sections or agencies. As [Iver Neumann \(2007\)](#) documents, this is a practice that typically serves to secure invariance; each state's main intervention can be predicted almost word for word in advance. Beyond adopting budgets and administrative decisions, the conferences in question seldom result in material output of any kind. Nevertheless, most states send delegations to several of these conferences each year, signaling their support for multilateral diplomacy and progressive change in the future. In the NPT review cycle, the neutral and nonaligned states ritualistically criticize the nuclear powers for their lack of action on the disarmament agenda. The nuclear-weapon states, for their part, predictably defend their track records and blame the lack of results on the "security environment." Other forums display similar dynamics. At the sessions of the Preparatory Commission of the CTBT, states parties religiously call for the universalization and entry-into-force of the treaty, the maintenance of the International Monitoring System (IMS), and protection of the norm against nuclear testing. Active involvement in these routines is widely seen as an end in and of itself, that is, as constitutive of sovereignty or statehood. In this perspective, mundane diplomatic routines become socially meaningful rituals when they are taken by their practitioners to signify something larger or more meaningful than their material outputs suggest ([Egeland 2025](#)).

The rituals associated with multilateral nuclear disarmament arguably serve multiple purposes. A first is the basic function of enabling reasonably ordered interaction between antagonistic states. Diplomatic protocol, norms, and rules of procedure exist to allow states with fundamentally conflicting preferences and worldviews to engage one another in a structured way. Crucially, delegations are expected to speak in turn, to demonstrate a modicum of respect for others, to praise and congratulate the conference chairperson or president, to honor the norms of seat rotation and the right to reply, and so on. These conventions are, for the most part, respected. Thus, while multilateral nuclear arms control and disarmament diplomacy unquestionably struggles to deliver forceful treaties, multilateral nuclear disarmament diplomacy "works" in the more basic sense that delegations are enabled to exchange views and present their respective positions in a reasonably ordered setting.

The rituals of multilateral arms control and disarmament can also serve to bind states together as partners nominally committed to shared norms and ends. In other words, they can serve to unify sets of actors—as when a resolution or document is collectively adopted—or to sustain overarching goals and values. Such ritual bonding or integration can undoubtedly be experienced quite sincerely by those involved but may also be cynically exploited for political purposes, for example, by actors eager to create a facade of agreement or paper over fundamental differences. For example, the adoption of consensus "final documents" at NPT review conferences has allowed nuclear-weapon-state officials to depoliticize multilateral nuclear disarmament diplomacy, portraying their nations as committed allies in the struggle to eliminate nuclear weapons ([Egeland 2025](#)). By the same token, failures to adopt resolutions or final documents are often perceived as ritual failures that bring the political fault lines underpinning multilateral arms control and disarmament diplomacy to the fore (a similar dynamic is visible in climate diplomacy; see, e.g., [Death 2011](#)). Major powers such as the United States have typically seen it as being in their in-

terest to avoid political contestation and "polarization" in the nonproliferation and disarmament regime (see, e.g., [Warnke 1978](#)).

Another function that is arguably served by multilateral nuclear arms control and disarmament diplomacy is that of giving a sense of voice and agency to relatively disempowered states (the fourth function discussed above). As discussed above, rituals have been found to help agents faced with difficult circumstances to recover and build a sense of control ([Tian et al. 2018](#)). According to [Jan Ruzicka \(2018, 379\)](#), the "institutionalization of [diplomatic] nonproliferation meetings as an endless process" provides non-nuclear-weapon states with "opportunities to vent spleen" by criticizing the nuclear powers for their lacking implementation of repeated disarmament pledges. These forums "allow state and nonstate actors to voice their frustrations with the nuclear weapon states, challenge perceived injustice, and maintain spaces for resistance." In a critical perspective, this function of faux empowerment can be seen to have helped perpetuate a tiered nuclear order that casts some states as more equal than others. However, non-nuclear-weapon states' recurring symbolic enactment of resistance to the hierarchical nuclear order can also be seen as a practice of sovereignty affirmation. After all, a permanently unequal nuclear order that divides the world into nuclear "haves" and "have-nots" appears "to violate one of the bedrock principles of the international state system, namely, that sovereign states have an equal right to security, self-defense, and self-help, including the possession of nuclear weapons" ([Tannenwald 2013, 304](#); see also [Müller and Paulus 2007, 87](#); [Herrera and Hymans 2011, 2](#); [Ritchie 2019](#)). Ritual diplomatic criticism of this unequal order can thus be understood as a means for nonnuclear states to visibly contest nuclear hierarchy and, by extension, reaffirm the integrity of the norm of sovereign equality. Sovereignty, as suggested above, is not a fact of nature, but rather "an ongoing accomplishment of practice" ([Wendt 1992, 413](#)), produced, maintained, and transformed through evolving diplomatic actions ([Sending, Pouliot, and Neumann 2015, 17](#)). In summary, the stylized routines of multilateral diplomacy have facilitated cooperation and communication between adversarial states in the context of nuclear arms control and disarmament. While the rituals involved are not unique to nuclear diplomacy—symbol-heavy adoption ceremonies and routinized incantation of national statements are staples of all multilateral diplomacy—the nuclear issue is subject to more multilateral meetings, instruments, and mechanisms than any other issue item on the United Nation's agenda.

Conclusion

Nuclear statecraft is shot through with stylized performances, repetitious actions, and eschatological imagery. In this article, I have argued that a ritual-theoretic approach can enrich the scholarship on global nuclear politics, offering fresh perspectives on pervasive practices and institutions. More specifically, I have maintained that rituals and ritualization can help military and state institutions tackle central challenges in nuclear statecraft. First, rituals and ritualization can help conjure conformity throughout the nuclear chain of command. While the cultivation of obedience is a key concern for all military institutions and service branches—according to [Carl von Clausewitz \(2010, 122\)](#) "there is nothing in war which is of greater importance than obedience"—insubordination poses a particularly acute challenge in the nuclear field ([Lewy 1961](#)). After all, operators could potentially be called upon to carry out orders that, if executed,

could lead to the deaths of hundreds of thousands, if not millions, of individuals and, in the final analysis, the destruction of modern human civilization (the orders might very well also be unlawful, leaving the operators in a difficult bind). Such orders would be likely to give anyone pause. Yet, for deterrence policies to be credible, relevant stakeholders must have at least some degree of faith that launch orders will in fact be executed and not stymied by hesitant operators. By promoting social bonding or providing ideological cover for extreme acts of violence, rituals can help steel weapon operators' resolve to carry out extreme orders.

Second, rituals and ritualization can help generate cross-national buy-in for nuclear policies. This dynamic is evident in nuclear-political forums set up to further alliance cohesion around nuclear strategy, such as the NATO Nuclear Planning Group, but is also on display in the behavior of the many cross-regional ginger groups set up to advance nuclear arms control and disarmament. Ritual practices can help states cultivate unity and "we-feeling," fostering group-based agency, ontological security, and the transmission of political imaginaries across time and space. By the same token, rituals can also serve to entrench belief systems, insulating them from evolutionary pressures, and in that way promote ideological conformism. While the subjects involved may privately believe the rituals or wider belief systems in question to be misguided, the shared scripts, recurring personal encounters, and bodily performances of carefully choreographed sacral symbolism associated with ritual practice can render dissent—and, ultimately, policy innovation—socially uncomfortable (Sloterdijk 1987, 5–6). Denmark's period as a so-called footnote country in NATO, a period that saw majorities in the Danish parliament repeatedly instructing the government and its ambassador to NATO to express formal dissent against policies such as the US Strategic Defense Initiative and deployment to Europe of modernized intermediate-range nuclear forces, is frequently described by both analysts and policymakers as "embarrassing," not "serious," "unwelcome," "awkward," or reflective of a "betrayal" (Bjøl 1986; Rasmussen 2003, 612; Ellemann-Jensen 2004, 173; Danish Institute for International Studies 2005, 94, 102; Petersen 2012). By formally expressing opposition to key US policies at the North Atlantic Council and NPG, Denmark disrupted the cohesion-building ritual of NATO summitry. The NPG, I have argued, should above all be seen as a liminal ritual that helps produce nonnuclear allies as beneficiaries of nuclear protection.

Third, rituals provide a crucial infrastructure for diplomatic signaling and the management of diplomatic encounters between antagonistic polities. Above, I discussed the rites and protocols that structure multilateral nuclear arms control and disarmament diplomacy. Here, rituals take the form of endlessly recurring meetings characterized by the observance of diplomatic protocol, application of strict rules of procedure, and projection of formulaic rhetoric bordering on incantation. The rituals of multilateral arms control and disarmament diplomacy, in particular those concerning diplomatic protocol and the enactment of rules of procedure, help states with radically opposing interests to exchange views in a reasonably structured way. While these exchanges are not always particularly meaningful or productive, the rituals of diplomacy force states into a rule-governed pattern of speech and behavior. The ever-present possibility of breaking with established practice also provides states with opportunities to communicate a sense of exception. Rituals can also function as vehicles for coping with intransigent obstacles or performing symbolic resistance to a situation deemed unacceptable. Above, I discussed how multilateral

nuclear disarmament diplomacy has allowed non-nuclear-weapon states to symbolically act out their opposition to enduring nuclear inequalities. In this light, multilateral arms control diplomacy can be seen as a coping ritual.

The findings presented above have important implications for longstanding debates in security studies. Most importantly, I suggest that the pervasiveness of rituals and ritualization in deterrence practice broadly understood indicates that deterrence is not straightforward, as suggested by members of the so-called simple deterrence school, but socially fraught and in need of continuous upkeep. Against the view that deterrence is "extremely robust, almost an automatic consequence of the presence of a minimum number of nuclear weapons" (Deudney 2018, 339) a ritual-theoretic reading of symbolic fields such as Russian nuclear orthodoxy and the NATO Nuclear Planning Group reveals that the maintenance of credible deterrence postures has depended—at any rate in the minds of those responsible for the enactment of deterrence policies—on the active production of social acceptance throughout the military chain of command and vis-à-vis allies and external audiences. That said, the present study has relied only on a limited number of plausibility probes. Further research should investigate the robustness of the various hypotheses and inferences outlined above, exploring their payoff in other areas of nuclear statecraft.

The findings above suggest that ritual theory offers a promising means of unearthing new insights about international relations generally and nuclear statecraft specifically. Beyond the cases discussed in this article, which all deserve more attention, there are several practices within the broader realm of nuclear politics that might profitably be studied with the analytical apparatus of ritual theory. One such practice is the application by nuclear-armed states of strict regimes of nuclear secrecy. As a prominent historian of nuclear secrecy points out, "the ritualistic aspects of being 'let in' on a secret can reinforce loyalty—the oaths, hushed ceremony, and grave warnings—seemingly heighten a sense of tribal belonging and encourage complicity" (Wellerstein 2021, 82). Other practices that might usefully be analyzed in a ritual-theoretic perspective include remembrance ceremonies (notably the annual events in Hiroshima and Nagasaki), the various practices involving the so-called nuclear football (the president's briefcase containing nuclear launch codes), and nuclear testing. Students of nuclear politics might also investigate the potential for "critical" rituals performed to upset prevailing norms and practices. Both qualitative and quantitative methods could yield important insights (see Xygalatas et al. 2011). In a broader sense, one might ask whether nuclear deterrence practice would even be possible without ritual.

I have argued throughout this paper that a focus on ritual can yield important insights to students of global nuclear politics. But what, if anything, can the nuclear case tell us about ritual? A first insight, dovetailing with the conclusion of the introduction to this special issue, is that rituals take on a particular importance when stakes are high; nuclear policy has uniquely high stakes, and nuclear statecraft is a uniquely ritualized area of international relations (the salience of Russian orthodoxy is higher in the nuclear realm than *any other branch* of the Russian military; the NPG is the *only* permanent issue-specific ministerial body within NATO; and multilateral nuclear arms control diplomacy is denser and more time-consuming than *any other area* of multilateral diplomacy; see Egeland 2025). A second insight underscored by the nuclear case is that rituals are typically shot through with power. Rituals invariably work to sustain or challenge power structures—and they are frequently deployed with such ends specifically in mind. Scholars of ritual and ritualization in in-

ternational relations would do well to bring power and ideology more firmly back in the frame.

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